

Two Verses (2:60 and 2:61) of Surah Al-Baqarah, Comparative Study of Brahui Translation Pattern.

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
59-70

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Volume:3, Issue:2, 2023

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

Liaquat Ali Sani

Associate Professor, Department of Brahui,
University of Balochistan Quetta

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

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Muneer Ahmed

Lecturer, Department of Brahui,
University of Balochistan Quetta

Abstract

This research paper aims to analyze and compare the Brahui translation patterns in two selected verses from Surah Al-Baqarah (Chapter 2) of the Quran. The study focuses on the linguistic aspects of translation, particularly examines how different cases, pronouns, verb inflections, and phrases are employed in translating the Arabic text into Brahui in two distinct verses. The verses chosen for analysis are 2:60 and 2:61, and the focus will be on the usage of different grammatical cases, pronouns, and verb inflections. The paper utilizes primary and secondary sources of Brahui translations, namely those by Dinpuri (1916) and Dinpuri (2019), as well as Lehri Alasari (1992). By conducting a comparative analysis of these translations, the paper aims to shed light on the specific linguistic characteristics of the Brahui language and its patterns in Quranic translation.

Keywords: Brahui language, Surah Al-Baqarah, translation, Dinpuri, Alasari.

Corresponding Author Email:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0019-4066>

liaqatsani81@gmail.com

fehmidabaloch@ogr.erbakan.edu.tr